

Women in the Teaching Profession: Problems and Challenges: A Special Reference To Female Lecturers

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Abstract : A teacher is a student's mentor, advisor, philosopher, and friend. A teacher not only influences the lives of students but also works for the betterment of society. The teacher is a role model. Many people believe that women can be better teachers than males since few attributes are necessary for this career, such as patience, care, and affection, and women have these qualities in greater abundance than men. Higher education has changed dramatically in recent decades, with new policies governing teacher workload. They must also fulfill additional research, extension, and corporate life obligations. Female teachers confront the issue of balancing work and family life in this situation. Thus the present study aims to know about the stress level and challenges faced by the female lectures of higher education. Furthermore, the study aims to clarify the real situation of Indian working women in the teaching profession as well as to identify the major issues confronting female lectures, and give suggestions to improve female lectures performance in their field. The current research uses the descriptive survey method. The convenience sampling method will be used to select 50 female lecturers working in colleges in Bangalore. A self-structured questionnaire will be used to collect data.

Key words: Higher education, working women, female lecturers, challenges, problems

Introduction

Teaching, a noble profession is a daunting and challenging task. It is rather evident that women are significantly over-represented in the profession of educators. As per the data from the education department, more than 80% of all teachers are women. A greater reason for this trend is that school, college timings make it easier for women to manage work and family. So, women who are ambitious and career-oriented as well as want to look after their household responsibilities find teaching to be the most convenient and valuable profession. For many years teaching was seen as a comfortable, stable job with predictable tasks to perform. However, now with pedagogy being as disruptive as it is, teachers who are reluctant to change and relearn are unable to keep up. In the present era, with the advent of new methodologies in teaching and the way digital and smart learning has made inroads into the field of education, the role of teachers has also greatly evolved over a period of time. Today, a teacher is faced with the arduous task of keeping him/herself abreast with the latest inventions and strides in the field of medicine, education, science, art and etc. Upgrading their skills and knowledge from time to time is thus necessary and is an utmost priority today. They are facing multifaceted problems and stresses due to increasing demand and expectations from the society. Social status, salaries and general service condition of women teachers are far from satisfactory. There are various kinds of problems which women teachers are frequently facing.

Classroom challenges are part of the life of a teacher, and a good teacher always overcomes them. Some of the common challenges teacher's faces include lack of teamwork, minimal personal time, working towards long-term goals, arguments and student excuses, work family balance etc. Addressing these challenges can help improve teachers' emotional well-being and enhance students' success rate, thereby improving the ultimate quality of education.

Objectives

1. It focuses status of women in teaching profession in colleges.
2. Analyze the constraints that lecturers face when managing their professional and family responsibilities.
3. To suggest the efforts needed to improve the performance of teaching staff in their profession.

Research methodology

The population of the study consisted of female lecturers in colleges in bangalore during the period of 18th may to 28th may 2022

Sample of the study: a questionnaire was developed on google form to get data

Information about the challenges faced by women lecturers in teaching profession.

Sample size of the study: total forty five female lecturers in colleges in bangalore were covered in the study.

Sample design: convenience sampling

Sources of data

The study involves critical evaluation and analysis of primary data. A questionnaire was designed and formulated to find out the problems

faced women lecturers in teaching profession. Secondary data is also used for the study. Data were extracted from various sources such as research articles, publications and authenticated websites.

Research instrument:

The tool used is questionnaire and personal interview. Following facts were kept in mind while preparing the questionnaire: We tried to construct the questionnaire in such a way that it would work as a logical component of a well-thought-out tabulation plan, as well as to write it in plain english. Multiple-choice questions make up the majority of the questions. We started by making a draught copy of the questionnaire to make sure the questions were in the right sequence We also paid special attention to the fact that the questionnaire should include simple

but clear instructions for the respondents so that they have no trouble answering the questions.

Data analysis

Women instructors play an important part in the entire development of the family; yet, they confront difficulty in balancing family and professional obligations. Working women, in general, serve as both money generators and primary carers for their families' children. Working women may find it difficult to fulfill both familial and professional obligations as a result of their multiple roles. In light of this context, this section looks at the difficulties women lecturers experience in balancing work and home responsibilities. Eight variables were established and evaluated independently in order to analyse the constraints experienced by female teachers. Data was collected from 45 female lecturers via an e-questionnaire.

Diagram: problems and challenges female lecturers in teaching profession

Challenges	Yes	No
Family support	88.9%	11.1%
Balance between home and working place	66.7%	33.3%
Respect from male members	68.9%	31.1%
Personal leave	42.2%	57.8%
Clerical work	84.1%	15.9%
Student interaction	28.9%	71.1%
Sanitary facility	53.3%	46.7%
Promotion in working place	68.9%	31.1%

Table: problems and challenges female lecturers in teaching profession

The results show that there were 28.9 percent of respondents aged 31 to 45, 26.7 percent of those aged 46 to 60, and 44.45 percent of those aged less than 30. Permanent lecturers

account for 35.6 percent, temporary lecturers account for 35.6 percent, and part-time lecturers account for 28.9%. The majority of women's faculties work because they want to and because

they need to. A total of 71 percent of female lecturers have difficulties as a result of working longer hours than required. However, 84 percent of female lecturers must engage in clerical work in the college, which is one of the problems they confront in balancing their family and their job. Furthermore, 52% of female professors felt that managing their family and profession is difficult when they are frequently asked to attend meetings after hours and this has gone on for a long time. The majority of them believe that official authorities do not respond quickly to complaints. 53.3 percent of faculty members do not have access to sanitary facilities in the workplace. Few faculties are experiencing difficulties as a result of a lack of family support, lack of respect from male faculty, difficulties taking personal leave, and difficulty with work promotion and student interaction. However, 88.9% of female lecturers believe that women will be required to work in the teaching profession in the future.

Findings

In our study, we found that temporary and part-time lecturers face difficulties communicating with students, difficulty taking leave, officials who do not act on their complaints and male professors who do not respect them. They can, however, strike a balance between career and family life. Permanent full-time lecturers, on the other hand, have no problems interacting with students or taking personal leave, and the official authority responds quickly to their complaints. Male faculty members respect them, but they need to work more than just teaching; they need to be involved in clerical work, and they face challenges managing their family and their profession. Working women are stressed, according to the survey, due to an imbalance of job, family, and social life. According to the above conversations, most female lecturers have issues connected to their incapacity to spend quality time with their families as a result of severe workloads that cause stress and work-family conflict. Many female lecturers suffer from psychological stress as a result of an unbalanced professional, family, and social lives. However female lecturers believe that women will be required to work in the teaching profession in the future.

Suggestions

There are many problems that female lecturers have to face .it is necessary to concentrate on a few aspects in order to make the employment of female professors more comfortable. The study reveals that a family-friendly policy and practice that encourages the involvement of lecturers as

well as the overall development of the community has implications. Social support issues and work-family balancing issues are not new. Social assistance must also improve in order to improve work-family balance. The findings also point to the importance of a family-friendly policy and its implementation in order to support women lecturers who make major contributions to their families, communities, and country. A working woman's ability to improve her social status is in her own hands. At home and in the office, women need to be more proactive and aware of their rights. Women's empowerment will not be achieved unless women decide to speak out against their exploitation, whether on an economic, social, or sexual basis. The policy's implementation must be closely monitored, and data on women's engagement in the organization must be evaluated on a regular basis. This will ensure that top management is aware of any gender discrepancies within the organization, and that appropriate efforts can be made to close those gaps. The woman who works outside the home needs the support of her husband and other family members. To allow them to employ her abilities outside of the home, they must share domestic tasks. Because india is a traditionally patriarchal and male-dominated nation, a significant elevation of working women's status in society will remain a distant dream without the positive and liberal mindset of the average indian male to encourage them. Seminars and workshops should be organized, and the value of education should be institutionalized through all socialization agents, such as religion, law, media, politics, and family. Aside from socioeconomic improvements, policies must be developed at the political level. Parents and family members should work together to encourage and motivate to progress. According to the poll, the firm exhibits a lack of respect for its employees. Special preparations for the care of female lecturers should be made. The first thing that society should take is to help working women feel more at ease. Inequality in the workplace affects a small number of female academics. Their grievances should be adequately heard. Salary increases should be made from time to time to incentivize and encourage them to continue with the company. . In the survey, it is noticed that temporary and part-time female lecturers are facing more problems as compared to the permanent full-time lecturers. Special provisions should be framed for temporary and part-time female lecturers so that they can adjust properly between personal life as well as

professional life and to motivate to stay in the organization. Efforts should be done to provide a familiar environment in the organization so that the stress level of women can be decreased.

Conclusion

Women's workplaces are being enhanced and promoted these days. Teaching must shed its status as the profession of last resort for females in society. Females should be encouraged to pursue other careers so that they are not obligated to teach if they wish to work. Also, the importance and responsibilities of a teacher's profession should be explained so that it is not misunderstood as an unappealing but available position. The goal of this study was to learn about the obstacles that female lecturers encounter in reconciling their roles as a mother and a professional. The study discovered that employing female lecturers in economic activity has a number of positive effects on the family's financial situation. Despite the importance of female lecturers in the overall development of the family, the majority of female lecturers face substantial challenges in reconciling their roles as mothers and teachers, particularly when they are required to work longer hours than usual. As a result, the majority of female lecturers experience psychological stress when they are unable to accomplish a work within a set time frame. While they spend significant amounts of time away from their young children and family, this might be a contributing factor to family conflict. Women's nature is a promotion to gain high quality in every field, but if the conditions are not ready, then the reduction of promotion and optimization in work will occur, and so on... Trade unions should try to improve the conditions for women's workers in many areas, for example, maternity leave is easily given to women and can help them achieve higher posts. Women's nature is a promotion to gain high quality in every field, but if the conditions are not ready, then the reduction of promotion and optimization in work will because women workers are frequently subjected to sexual harassment, the government should impose strong penalties for such crimes. Additionally, public transportation can be risky for women, and the government should conduct more inspections. Given the value and requirements of female participation in the teaching profession. Therefore a fundamental change is required in the attitudes of employees, family members, and public.

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